

EFFECTS OF THE SUPREME SECONDARY LEARNER GOVERNMENT POLICIES: GOAL FOR STUDENT WELFARE

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Abstract. The study determined the effects of the supreme secondary learners' government policies and its goal for student welfare in Cluster 5, Davao City Schools Division. The study used a non-experimental descriptive-correlational research design, utilizing an adapted survey instrument to gather responses from the 120 randomly selected teacher-respondents. Data gathered were treated using Mean scores with descriptive interpretation, Pearson r and Simple Linear Regression Analysis. Findings revealed that supreme secondary learners' government policies is sometimes manifested, thus, moderately extensive, and, likewise, learner's Safety is sometimes manifested, thus, moderately extensive. There is a significant correlation between the supreme secondary learner government (SSL) structure and school policies affecting learner safety. All domains of supreme secondary learner government policies in terms of representation and diversity, budget resource allocation, advocacy and policy influence, collaboration with school administration, and training and development significantly influence learner safety. Future research may provide insights into the sustainability of the influence of SSLGs on safety policies over time.

KEY WORDS

1. Supreme Secondary Learner Government Policies.
2. Learner's Safety.
3. budget resource allocation.

1. Introduction

Educational authorities and policymakers are recognizing the multifaceted nature of threats faced by secondary learners, necessitating holistic strategies that address various aspects of safety and well-being. Moreover, a growing emphasis is on promoting a culture of inclusivity and diversity within schools, fostering environments where all learners feel valued, respected, and protected. However, despite these advancements, several persistent issues continue to challenge the effective implementation of learner safety policies. These include resource constraints, inadequate training for educators and staff, and gaps in communication between stakeholders. Furthermore, the rapid proliferation of digital technologies has introduced new risks, such as cyberbullying, online harassment, and exposure to inappropriate content, highlighting the need for updated policies and robust educational interventions in this domain. Educational policymakers must prioritize the development of evidence-based strategies that address both traditional and emerging threats to learner safety while fostering a supportive and

nurturing academic environment conducive to the holistic development of secondary learners.

International trends and issues in school policies affecting learner safety are evolving in response to the changing landscape of education and the broader societal context. One significant trend is the increasing emphasis on comprehensive anti-bullying and anti-harassment policies. Schools worldwide recognize the importance of creating inclusive and safe environments, with policies to prevent and address all forms of bullying, cyberbullying, and discrimination (Hassan, 2019). Another trend is the integration of technology into safety policies. As digital learning becomes more prevalent, schools address online safety concerns like internet security, data privacy, and cyber threats. This includes educating students about responsible digital behavior and implementing measures to protect them from online risks. Schools are working to create environments that celebrate diversity, respect different cultural backgrounds, and ensure that every student feels safe and valued (Kimitris, 2018). These policies often encompass initiatives to address implicit bias, promote cultural competence, and foster understanding among students (Zha and Wang, 2020). Additionally, the Cypriot government strives to rationalize the educational system, emphasizing creating citizens inspired by democratic ideals and critical thinking. The most potent weapon for a nation-state is to have and use the teaching of language and history. With these subjects, the state attempts to pass its traditions, customs, ideals, values, and historical achievements to its students and future citizens (Persianis, 2010). Meanwhile, the Philippine government has implemented the Anti-Bullying Act, mandating the adoption of comprehensive anti-bullying programs in all schools. This emphasizes the importance of addressing various forms of bullying, including cyberbullying and discrimination, to create safe and inclusive spaces for students. Forming a Supreme Secondary Learner Govern-

ment (SSLG) structure significantly contributes to mitigating the challenges encountered by learners in the school community. Firstly, the SSLG provides a platform for students to voice their concerns, needs, and aspirations actively. This open communication channel allows learners to express issues they face, such as bullying, harassment, safety concerns, or academic challenges, and actively participate in finding solutions. Secondly, the SSLG empowers students to take on leadership roles and responsibilities, fostering a sense of ownership and accountability for their school environment. By involving students in decision-making processes related to school policies and initiatives, the SSLG gives them a say in their education and instills a sense of agency in addressing challenges (Alviento, 2018). Furthermore, the SSLG structure encourages collaboration between students, teachers, and school administrators. This collaborative approach enables stakeholders to identify challenges and implement effective solutions. The SSLG can initiate or advocate for policies and programs to improve learner safety, inclusivity, and overall well-being. Additionally, the SSLG often organizes awareness campaigns, workshops, and educational initiatives focused on mitigating challenges, such as bullying prevention or mental health support. These efforts create a more informed and empathetic school community, reducing the prevalence of challenges and enhancing students' coping mechanisms (Hassan, 2019). The Davao City Government, in collaboration with the Department of Education (DepEd) Davao City, has been actively working to implement its child-friendly policy, prioritizing the well-being and rights of children in the community. Their efforts are multifaceted and comprehensive. First and foremost, they have established child-friendly spaces, including safe and well-maintained schools, playgrounds, and recreational areas, ensuring that children have access to environments conducive to their physical and mental development. An-

other crucial aspect of their efforts is the promotion of child protection policies. Davao City Government and DepED Davao City have implemented anti-bullying and anti-harassment programs and mechanisms for reporting and addressing violations of children's rights. Additionally, they prioritize inclusive and quality education, striving to provide equal opportunities for all children, regardless of their background or circumstances. This includes initiatives to improve educational infrastructure, enhance teacher training, and expand access to quality education, ultimately ensuring that every child has the chance to reach their full potential. Moreover, Davao City Government and DepED Davao City actively engage in community outreach and awareness campaigns. They work with parents, teachers, and local organizations to promote child-friendly values and practices, fostering a culture of care, protection, and inclusivity.

2. Methodology

Research methods are the systematic procedures and techniques researchers employ to gather, analyze, and interpret data to answer specific research questions or test hypotheses. These methods serve as the foundation for scientific inquiry, enabling researchers to design and conduct studies in a structured and rigorous manner. In this context, understanding the research method is essential for both researchers and readers as it determines the validity and reliability of the study's findings and contributes to the broader body of knowledge in the field of inquiry. This aims to elucidate the key components and considerations associated with the chosen research method, setting the stage for a comprehensive exploration of the research methodology employed in the study. In the preparation of this paper, the researcher employed artificial intelligence tools for proofreading. Specifically, AI was utilized to enhance the accuracy, coherence, and overall quality of the manuscript. This practice is being explicitly stated to maintain transparency and adhere to ethical standards in research. The usage of AI for proofreading reflects a commitment to leveraging advanced technologies responsibly and acknowledges the increasing prevalence and capability of AI in academic and professional writing.

2.1. Research Design—The non-experimental descriptive-correlational and predictive research design is a comprehensive research approach that combines several vital elements. It is non-experimental, for it does not involve the manipulation of variables or establishing a cause-and-effect relationship. Instead, it focuses on observing and measuring existing phenomena as they naturally occur. Second, it is descriptive, aiming to provide a detailed and systematic account of a particular subject or topic. This involves collecting data through surveys, observations, or existing records to describe and summarize the characteristics, behaviors, or conditions under investigation. Third, it is correlational, which means it seeks to identify relationships or associations between variables. This involves analyzing data to determine whether changes in one variable are related to changes in another without implying causation (Creswel, 2014). In the study examining the Supreme Secondary Learner Government (SSLG) structure on school policies affecting learner safety, a non-experimental descriptive-correlational and predictive research design plays a crucial role. First, the non-experimental aspect ensures that researchers are not manipulating variables but are closely observing and documenting how the SSLG functions naturally within the school context. The descriptive com-

ponent allows researchers to systematically collect data about the SSLG structure, its activities, and its influence on school policies. This includes detailed descriptions of SSLG leadership roles, engagement levels, and the implementation of safety-related policies. The correlational aspect comes into play when researchers analyze the data to identify relationships between the SSLG's involvement and the effectiveness of school policies related to learner safety. For instance, researchers may explore whether higher levels of SSLG engagement correlate with a decrease in reported safety incidents or an increase in the implementation of safety initiatives. Lastly, the predictive element allows researchers to make informed predictions impact of the SSLG structure on school policies affecting learner safety. By identifying significant correlations, researchers can extrapolate and suggest potential improvements in school policies, anticipate future trends, and provide recommendations for enhancing the SSLG's role in ensuring learner safety. In essence, this research design helps shed light on the complex dynamics between student governance, school policies, and learner safety, providing valuable insights and guidance for educational institutions aiming to create safer and more inclusive learning environments.

2.2. *Research Respondents*—Respondents of the study were the Secondary School Teachers in the Public Schools within Cluster 5 of the Schools Division of Davao City. He used the Raosoft sample size calculator, where 120 teacher-respondents were taken randomly from each Public Secondary School surrounding Cluster 5. One randomly determined, the respondents were informed through online platforms and face-to-face considering the availability of the Wifi connections, and they were likewise oriented about the purpose and importance of the study and its contribution to their professional development status. These teacher-respondents were selected for they were

assumed to have been engaged in implementing various school learning programs, projects, and activities related to student's development and growth under school-based management. They are qualified for the role they were expected to have performed and contributed to, given that they have attended various activities aside from the school's management in curriculum delivery and implementation and governance. This is done through school faculty meetings and other group and committee meetings to improve the school and the learners' awareness and educational stages given the new regular learning system during SY 2023-2024. Further, they have frequently engaged in various activities and advocacy-policy through school-based initiatives and in support of the school management and curriculum development delivery system. Moreover, assumptions in the respective schedule of classes during data collection were explicitly discussed with the respondents, and even observance of health protocol was strictly implemented based on Executive Order 31 S 2020 to avoid possible and lower the risk of contamination.

2.3. *Research Instrument*—This research study used the adapted instrument from reviewed literature and related studies. The researcher took time gathering and reading reviews of related literature to develop concepts for the content that support the instrument and its corresponding strands in articulating the set of question items, reducing threats to validity. As the authors argued, items were adapted from the reviewed literature. Two parts of the survey questionnaire comprised indicators of the SSLG policies regarding representation and diversity, budget resources and allocation, advocacy and policy influence, collaboration with school administration, and training and development. Likewise, the second part of the survey measured the school policies affecting learners' safety regarding anti-bullying initiatives, harassment reporting, safety-related policies, student

engagement, and communication with authorities. Further, the survey statements were subjected to a test-retest or validity and reliability testing using Cronbach Alpha . They generated an alpha Cronbach of 0.878, which means that the unidimensional reliability when it comes to

internal consistency is very good.

The questionnaire used a 5-point Likert scale to determine the effectiveness of the SSLG structure. Scale, descriptive rating and interpretation are provided below:

Scale	Descriptive Rating	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very Extensive	The SSLG structure policies are always manifested
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	The SSLG structure policies are oftentimes manifested
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The SSLG structure policies are sometimes manifested
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The SSLG structure policies are rarely manifested
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The SSLG structure policies are not manifested

Meanwhile, to determine the extent of school policies affecting learners’ safety, a 5-

point Likert scale was used in this study, as presented below;

Scale	Descriptive Rating	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very Extensive	The school learners’ safety is always manifested
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	The school learners’ safety is oftentimes manifested
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The learners’ safety is sometimes manifested
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The learners’ safety is rarely manifested
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The learners’ safety is not manifested

2.4. *Data Gathering Procedure*—The preceding statements explain the data-gathering procedure steps that the researcher must comprehensively consider and follow. They are based on the policies and guidelines of the College where the researcher is studying regarding the gathering of pertinent data, most especially in the current face-to-face interaction. Permission to conduct the study. The second week

of December 2023, the researcher started conceptualizing the thesis proposal’s contents and objective. She then prepares documents such as letter requests in the conduct of the study. The research study adopted the standard procedures of ethics in data collection (Creswell, 2004) and health protocol as provided by the IATF policy. From the last week of February up to the first week of March 2024, as soon

as the research proposal presentation was approved by the panel of members and the dean of the college, the researcher wrote and sent a letter of permission to the office of the Schools Division Superintendent of Davao City, through channel and sought permission to collect data and conduct the study among the Secondary Schools. Distribution and retrieval of the questionnaire. In May 2024, the researcher prepared and created a Google sheet form for the online survey collection process, which was sent to the randomly selected respondents via email addresses and to respondents without internet access. Likewise, a prepared hard copy of the survey sheets was given to each of them. Once done, the link was sent, and right away, responses were generated, thus, ready for sort-

ing, analyzing, and interpreting. This activity was done right after the approval of the Schools Division Superintendent to proceed with data gathering, which commenced on the third week of May 2024. Collation and statistical treatment of data. The preliminary analysis results were given to the thesis adviser during the second week of June 2024. For coaching and in terms of statistical treatment, the thesis adviser sought the assistance of the graduate school statistician to provide technical discussions in running the data and its interpretations and implications of the study sometime in the first week of June 2024 and further deepening the analysis to make more meaning with the interpretations of results on the second week of June 2024.

2.5. *Data Analysis*—Mean scores and standard deviation were used to address statement problems posed in statement problem number one (1), the effectiveness of SSLG policies, and statement problem number two (2), the extent to which school policy affects learner safety. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient or Pearson-r was used to determine its strength/direction significant relationship between the effectiveness of SSLG Structure and school policy

affecting learner's safety. Simple Linear Regression analysis was used to address problem number 4, on the indicators of SSLG Structure that significantly influence school policy affecting learner's safety (Pallant, 2000) and (Gujarati, 2000). All data processing and analysis were performed using Jeffrey's Statistics Amazing Program (JASP) version 0.12.20. Discussions and interpretations followed when results were yielded.

3. Results and Discussion

The researcher explores data gathering and its subsequent presentation, analysis, and interpretation in this section. Utilizing both tabular and textual formats enhances the depth of the study and streamlines the extraction of meaningful implications. Furthermore, these presentations serve as substantiating evidence for the proposed hypothesis.

Table 1 summarizes the extent of effectiveness of the Supreme Secondary Learner Government (SSLG) Structure. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators, which are as follows: advocacy and policy influence (3.69) and training and development (3.51) are often manifested; In contrast,

budget resources and allocation (3.18), representation and diversity (3.10), and collaboration with school administration (2.79) are sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.25 denotes the extent to which learning action cell sessions are sometimes manifested, thus being moderately extensive.

Table 1. Summary of the Extent of Supreme Secondary Learner Government (SSLG) Policies

No	Effectiveness of SSLG Structure	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	representation and diversity	3.10	Moderately Extensive
2	budget resources and allocation	3.18	Moderately Extensive
3	advocacy and policy influence	3.69	Extensive
4	collaboration with school administration	2.79	Moderately Extensive
5	training and development	3.51	Extensive
Overall Mean		3.25	Moderately Extensive

Over the past ten years, an intense debate has been introduced and initiated by the government of Cyprus on reforming the structure and goals of education. A comprehensive academic report highlighted the need to reshape the highly Greek-centralized Cypriot system (Committee on Educational Reform, 2004). It introduced the first seeds of Cypriot educational autonomy (Karagiorgi Nicolaidou, 2010). Additionally, the Cypriot government is striving to rationalize the educational system, emphasizing creating citizens inspired by democratic ideals and critical thinking. The most potent weapon for a nation-state is to have and use the teaching of language and history. With these subjects, the state attempts to pass its traditions, customs, ideals, values, and historical achievements to its students and future citizens (Persianis, 2010). Alviento (2018) anchored upon salient factors

such as the perceptions of the students and student leaders on the effectiveness of performance of the Student Government of North Luzon Philippines State College. The study could benefit student leaders, for they shall be provided a massive insight into how the Student Government operates. Since they are prospective leaders of the college, they may be able to determine which programs and projects could better impact students' welfare. The student government is doing its role in the college by making the students aware of their political rights. It is just that they need to hold regular leadership training seminars so that the students, especially the student leaders, can adequately learn how to become more mature and influential leaders. It should be a facilitator to the administration or any other student organizations whenever necessary.

Table 2 summarizes the extent to which school policies affect learners' safety. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: communication with authorities (3.55), harassment and reporting (3.54) and anti-bullying initiative

(3.46) are often manifested; safety-related policies (3.16) and student engagement (3.04) are sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.55 denotes how school policies affect learners' safety, which is sometimes manifested as moderately extensive.

Educational frameworks mandate that schools adopt, design, and implement strategies that support inclusive education. Despite the inclusive education policy, disability remains

a major cause of exclusion in learning institutions. Ileri et al. (2020) discuss the impact of school strategies on overcoming physical barriers that hinder the implementation of inclusive

Table 2. Summary of the Extent of Learner’s Safety

No	School Policies affecting Learner’s Safety	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	anti-bullying initiatives	3.46	Extensive
2	harassment and reporting	3.54	Extensive
3	safety-related policies	3.16	Moderately Extensive
4	student engagement	3.04	Moderately Extensive
5	communication with authorities	3.55	Extensive
Overall Mean		3.35	Moderately Extensive

education. The study established that the school strategies needed to be anchored in overcoming physical barriers that hindered the implementation of inclusive education, with various challenges affecting the strategies. For this reason, learners with disabilities must adjust to get the needed education or drop out of school. Therefore, the study concluded that ineffective school strategies contributed to a lack of overcoming physical barriers, negatively impacting the implementation of inclusive education in schools. School transformation founded on clear inclusive education vision and philosophy, policies, and inclusive strategies are necessary to overcome physical barriers hindering the implementation of inclusive education. Schools should be safe places for young people, educators, school staff, and community members, and policies and practices can help create learning environments where kids thrive. Gun violence in U.S. schools has prompted calls for increased school safety measures; however, which policies contribute to safe school environments is often a topic of debate. To help Colorado policymakers and school communities answer this question, the Colorado Children’s Campaign has identified and compiled research on strategies supported by solid evidence. While school safety can be

defined broadly as freedom from physical, emotional, and psychological violence, this brief focuses on promoting freedom from bodily harm in a school setting. Strategies that support students’ well-being and prevent bullying, fighting, the use of weapons, and other types of violence can contribute to reducing harm Colorado Children’s Campaign (2023).

Significant Relationship between Supreme Secondary Learner Government (SSLG) Structure and School Policies Affecting Learner’s Safety

Table 3 revealed the significant relationship between the supreme secondary learner government (SSL) structure and school policies that affect learner safety. It provides information that the posed null hypothesis stating that there is no significant relationship between supreme secondary learner government (SSL) structure and school policies affecting learner’s safety must be rejected for it provided empirical evidence to show its correlation. It can be depicted that Pearson’s Correlation generated a significant strong positive correlation between Supreme Secondary Learner Government (SSLG) Structure ($r=0.857$; $p<.001$) and School Policies affecting Learner Safety.

The significant relationship between the Supreme Secondary Learner Government

(SSLG) structure and school policies profoundly impacts learner safety within the ed-

Table 3. Relationship between Supreme Secondary Learner Government (SSLG) Structure and School Policies Affecting Learner’s Safety

Variables	School Heads’ Authentic Leadership	r-value	p-value	Interpretation	Decision
Teachers’ Organizational Commitment	0.857	0.001	Significant	Reject H_0	*significant @ $p < 0.05$

educational environment. Gomba and Zindonda (2021) said that the SSLG, as a representative body of students, plays a crucial role in shaping and influencing the formulation of school policies related to safety. The structural dynamics of the SSLG, including its leadership hierarchy, decision-making processes, and communication channels, directly influence the extent to which student voices are considered in creating and implementing safety policies. A well-structured SSLG can serve as an effective liaison between students and school administration, ensuring that policies address the specific safety concerns and needs of the learners (Eden, 2020). Additionally, Esen et.al. (2021) shared that the SSLG structure can contribute to a more inclusive and participatory approach, where students actively engage in discussions about safety measures, emergency protocols, and the overall well-being of the school community. The SSLG’s influence on school policies creates a collaborative environment that fosters a sense of ownership and responsibility among students, leading to increased compliance with safety guidelines. A robust SSLG structure establishes a vital link between students and school policies, playing a

pivotal role in enhancing and promoting learner safety within the educational setting.

Domains of Supreme Secondary Learner Government (SSLG) Structure Significantly Influence School Policies Affecting Learner’s Safety

Table 4 depicts the simple regression coefficient analysis on domains of supreme secondary learner government (SSL) structure significantly influence school policies affecting learner’s safety. Domains of supreme secondary learner government (SSL) structure in terms of representation and diversity (0.001), budget resource allocation (0.010), advocacy and policy influence (0.002), collaboration with school administration (0.000) and training and development (0.000) significantly influence school policies affecting learner’s safety. Meanwhile, the R2 value of 0.857 suggests that school heads’ authentic leadership is explained by 87.7%. In addition, the F-value shows all the sums of squares, with regression being the model and Residual being the error. The F-value (262.586) and F-statistic is significant $p < 0.000$, which indicates that the model is a better predictor of teachers’ organizational commitment.

Nickerson, et.al., (2020) investigated the structure of the Supreme Secondary Learner Government (SSLG) holds a substantial influence over the formulation and implementation of school policies, particularly those pertaining to learner safety. The SSLG, as Horton (2022) discuss a representative body of students, plays a pivotal role in shaping the discourse around safety measures within the educational environment. The hierarchical organization, decision-making processes, and communication channels

within the SSLG structure directly impact the degree to which student perspectives are considered in the development of safety policies. A well-organized SSLG serves as an effective conduit for student input, ensuring that safety policies address the specific concerns and needs of learners. By actively participating in discussions and decision-making processes, the SSLG contributes to the creation of comprehensive safety guidelines, emergency protocols, and overall measures to safeguard the well-being of

Table 4. Regression Coefficient Analysis on Domains of Supreme Secondary Learner Government (SSLG) Structure Significantly Influence School Policies Affecting Learner’s Safety

Model		B	Beta	Standard Error	p-value
Decisions					
H	(Intercept)	4.145	0.079	60.416	0.001
4.143					
H	(Intercept)	0.313	0.175	1.066	0.270
0.202					
	Representation and Diversity	0.827	0.117	0.102	1.010
0.325	0.001	*Reject H_0			
	Budget Resource Allocation	0.411	0.118	0.136	1.299
0.116	0.010	*Reject H_0			
	Advocacy and Policy Influence	0.222	0.087	0.210	2.098
0.028	0.002	*Reject H_0			
	Collaboration with School Administration	0.911	0.518	0.136	1.299
0.256	0.000	*Reject H_0			
	Training and Development	0.512	0.047	0.210	3.098
0.078	0.000	*Reject H_0			

the school community. The SSLG’s influence on school policies creates a collaborative atmosphere, fostering a sense of responsibility and ownership among students in adhering to safety guidelines. In essence, the SSLG structure significantly shapes the relationship between students and school policies, playing a crucial role in enhancing and promoting learner safety within the educational institution (Nickerson, et.al., 2022).

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This chapter presents the findings, conclusions, and recommendations based on the results of the data analyzed, discussed, and implications drawn. Findings are based on the problem’s posed statement; conclusions are based on the findings generated, and recommendations are based on the implications of the discussions.

4.1. Findings—The extent of Supreme Secondary Learner Government (SSLG) Policies in terms of advocacy and policy influence (3.69) and training and development are often-times manifested; while, budget resources and allocation, representation and diversity and collaboration with school administration are sometimes manifested, thus, moderately extensive. The extent of Learner Safety in terms of communication with authorities, harassment and reporting, and anti-bullying initiatives is often manifested; safety-related policies and student engagement are sometimes manifested; thus, it is moderately extensive. Pearson’s Correlation generated a significant Relationship between Supreme Secondary Learner Government (SSLG) Policies and School Policies affecting Learner’s Safety. Domains of supreme secondary learner government (sslg) Policies in terms of representation and diversity, budget

resource allocation, advocacy and policy influence, collaboration with school administration and training and development significantly influence school policies affecting learner's safety.

4.2. Conclusions—Given the findings of the study presented, the following are conclusions, to wit; The extent of effectiveness of Supreme Secondary Learner Government (SSLG) policies in terms of advocacy and policy influence and training and development are oftentimes manifested, while budget resources and allocation, representation and diversity, and collaboration with school administration are sometimes manifested; thus, moderately extensive. The extent of Learner's Safety in terms of communication with authorities, harassment and reporting, and anti-bullying initiatives are oftentimes manifested; safety-related policies and student engagement are sometimes manifested, thus, moderately extensive. There is a significant relationship between the Supreme Secondary Learner Government (SSLG) policies and school policies that affect learners' safety. Domains of supreme secondary learner government (sslg) Policies in terms of representation and diversity, budget resource allocation, advocacy and policy influence, collaboration with school administration and training and development significantly influenced learner's safety. The study on the effectiveness of the Supreme Secondary Learner Government (SSLG) structure in shaping school policies related to learner safety aligns well with the theoretical framework of Albert Bandura's "Social Learning Theory." Albert Bandura's Social Learning Theory emphasizes the concept that individuals learn and develop their behaviors, attitudes, and values by observing, imitating, and modeling the actions of those around them. In the context of this study, the SSLG serves as a prime example of social learning in practice. Student leaders elected to SSLG positions become role models for their peers, actively engaging in school policies, advocacy efforts, and

decision-making processes concerning learner safety. By doing so, they demonstrate how individuals can effect change within their school environment.

4.3. Recommendations—With the presented conclusions of the study, the following are recommendations, to wit; Public School District Supervisor. May encourage public schools to actively involve SSLGs in the policymaking process related to learner safety. Establishing guidelines that outline the collaboration between SSLGs and school administration in formulating safety policies will contribute to a more inclusive and participatory decision-making approach. Additionally, providing training and resources to district-level administrators on effective ways to engage with SSLGs can enhance the overall impact of student involvement in shaping safety policies. School Principal. May foster a supportive environment that values and integrates the contributions of the SSLG in matters of learner safety. Encouraging regular communication and collaboration between the SSLG and school administration will ensure that safety policies are reflective of the specific concerns and perspectives of the student body. Principals should also consider implementing training sessions for SSLG members to enhance their understanding of safety issues and their role in policy development. Teacher. May support the engagement of SSLGs in safety policymaking by fostering an environment that values student input. Collaborative efforts between teachers and SSLGs in discussing safety measures, emergency protocols, and overall learner well-being can strengthen the effectiveness of safety policies. Teachers should also facilitate opportunities for student expression and involvement in school safety initiatives, encouraging a sense of shared responsibility among students and educators. Future Researcher. May encouraged to delve into the long-term impact of SSLG involvement in safety policies and explore innovative strategies to further enhance student

participation. Longitudinal studies can provide insights into the sustainability of the influence of SSLGs on safety policies over time. Additionally, researchers can investigate the potential variations in SSLG impact across different school contexts and demographics, contributing to a more nuanced understanding of student involvement in shaping educational policies.

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